

Assessing Performance and Equity of Grade Separators in Heterogeneous Traffic: An Ex-Post Evaluation

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ABSTRACT: This paper presents an ex-post-performance evaluation of four grade separators (flyovers) in Nagpur, India, focusing on equity and efficiency in heterogeneous traffic. Using the moving observer method and six performance indices, the study compares access- controlled (above-grade) and residual (at-grade) link performance during peak hours.

The analysis reveals that while flyovers benefit faster motorized traffic, they significantly increase delays and unreliability for at-grade users (including NMTs) by reducing effective carriageway width. The study concludes that flyovers are non-equitable interventions that marginalize slower modes. These results highlight the need for decision-makers in developing economies to rethink urban interventions to ensure benefits are distributed across all transport modes.

KEY WORDS: Delay, Efficiency, Equity, Heterogeneous Traffic, Grade Separators, Interventions, Travel Time, User Benefits, Reliability, Variability.

1. INTRODUCTION

The fast pace of urbanization in India and its consequent demographic change has seen a rising trend in vehicular ownership and mobility on roads. Congestion is one of the outcomes of such a situation and mitigation measures often result in providing interventions to improve mobility. The development of robust and high-speed transport links capable of carrying large volumes of traffic fosters connectivity and boosts economic growth. Development, however, is also a base for intervention provision other than only as mitigation measures to perceived or real mobility issues. Most measures for high speed mobility on the urban road networks are necessarily provided by augmenting existing road infrastructure by widening them or retrofitting with grade separators. But post provision the performance of such measures is rarely attempted to ascertain their efficacy and efficiency and ex-post studies are rarely done (Bonilla and Urbanik, 1987, Liyanage, 2009, Suh and Yeo, 2015)

Studies have focused primarily on assessing ex ante evaluations and mostly with a diagnostic focus for determination and recommendation of further improvements or provision of mitigation measures. (Berechman and Paaswell, 2005). However, there is a growing emphasis on performance evaluations of transport, its systems and its component around the world, especially in the developed economies (Cortwright, 2010, Ogunleye, 2013, DOT UK, 2014). Academic research available has explored the varied aspects of performance evaluation metrics and practices (Litman, 2014). Researchers seem to be divided on the most suitable Performance metrics for different user groups, context and agencies. Therefore, measures used in studies range from ascertaining the QOS, LOS, Fuel efficiency, emission reduction to the most traditionally accepted metrics based on travel time –delay depending on the focus of the study (Lomax et al., 2003). But most studies have and are focused on the automobile and the systems benefits to it and their long-term effects have rarely been assessed Though highways are the primary roads evaluated for performance arterials are major connectors in core urban areas in Indian cities and hence their evaluation is more important for delineating issues which affect them and influence their output. (Bharti et al., 2018) In Indian road conditions where heterogeneous traffic is a unique characteristic, performance evaluation to determine the effectiveness and efficiency of an intervention becomes highly significant not only for the sake of conducting appraisal but also from a perspective of equitable distribution of benefits and types and degree of impacts and should inform future decision making. It is with this focus that the study was designed as an ex post performance evaluation of grade separators as mobility enhancing measures which are built structures giving impetus to faster modes but impacting the mobility of all modes on their residual component considerably.

The aim of this study is: 1) to investigate the grade separator as an effective and reliable component of the urban transportation system 2) to compare performance and degree of reliability when compared to its residual link (at-grade). 3) to ascertain the degree to which it is efficient and effective. The study additionally investigates two interrelated concepts of travel time

and delay studies, variability and reliability exploring them from the perspective of equity by establishing the variation in measures of both links. Contemporary urban environment presents complex challenges to the planners and interventions are planned and provided for but are they really effective and efficient as a system and to what extent do they fulfil their role in easing urban mobility. The study attempts to find out and herein lies its significance.

In the transport planning domain researchers and academics have relied more on direct travel time and delay performance metrics than other indicators as evidence of the efficiency and effectiveness of a route, link or network (Higatani et al., 2009; Wakabayashi and Matsumoto, 2012; Chalumuri and Yasao, 2014; Jung, 2018) and. Studies mainly revolve around developing models to minimize delays or either improvement in travel times or both. Improving a systems efficiency is also a precursor to benchmarking its performance level (Lomax et al, 2003, TTI, 2005)

1.1 Study Area:

Nagpur, a city established on the Nag River has an evolutionary trajectory which is 300 years old .It shares some similar and some unique growth attributes to other cities in India. It has mostly a radial pattern of streets and has a disposition towards radial and circumferential growth mostly concentrated along its links .The city is a blend of old and new areas and densely populated towards the core of its radial expansion. The city has a population of 24 lakhs with moderate to extreme climatic conditions. The expansion of the city has been driven by the SEZ and MIHAN as also by the tremendous impetus to developmental projects in the last 3 decades. Although the population growth is moderate, the vehicular growth rate in comparison is faster. As per Census of India, 2011. with an area of 218 km² the population density per square kilometer is 11,056 persons /km². Nagpur also boasts a staggering number of flyovers and ring roads built for connectivity and growth as a regional hub.

The socio economic and the urban structure are the main factors which contribute to the traffic being mixed mode. With a decadal growth rate of 14.39 % the vehicle registration has a decadal growth of 10.79 %.(Figure 1) .To cater to this rising vehicular population road capacity has been increased in various forms, one of which is constructing flyovers along main arterials in core area to decongest them. The city boasts of 4 flyovers all belong to the parallel category while there are others which are connectors over railway lines crisscrossing the city or the great Nag River and its tributaries. The traffic of the city is mixed mode and hence the study requisites were ideally found as described in the methodology section.

Figure 1: Vehicle Registration
(Source : RTO Nagpur City).

2. METHODOLOGY

This empirical study compares the efficiency and efficacy of access control links with that of its residual component at grade. The study also investigates two inter related concepts of travel time and delay studies, variability and reliability establishing the degree of variation of indicators and measures used of each link. The study uses a set of six indicators and statistical measures as tools to establish the difference in performance of the systems two components and their degree of variation. Data was obtained using the moving car method. 20 run times were conducted on each component of the link in fair weather conditions and when traffic peak hour flow conditions were normal or near normal (without events). Therefore, the total sample size was 320 runs since the number of flyovers studied were four and directional links studied were 8 both directions (4 flyovers, 2 directions, 2 components and 20 runs each = 320 total runs). The FFS (Free Flow Speeds) were taken as 60 km/hr on all above grade links as they are links which were access controlled and at grade links it was 45 kms/hr. for calculating the indices. The measures obtained were statistically processed and interpreted to establish their respective and cumulative efficiency and effectiveness. For spot speeds data was collected and used from videography at select locations along links for weekdays during peak hour and off peak periods only during fair weather conditions. The six derived performance metrics used in the analysis viz. skew statistics, the misery index, the travel rate index in lieu of travel time index, the variability index and the 80th percentile travel rate index, percent variation are explained herein. (TTI,2005; Lomax et al, 2003, NAP ,2014)

- Skew Statistics is the ratio of (90th percentile travel time minus the median) divided by (the median minus the 10th percentile).
- Misery Index—The negative aspect of a trip reliability can be examined by the average number of minutes that the worst trips exceed the average. it is calculated by taking data from the worst 5% to 20% of the trips and finding their average travel rate for just those trips. Comparing that to the average travel rate for all trips gives a measure of worst days. The use of the percent value might be explained as focusing on the worst time or day of the observation period.
- Variability Index—A view of the reliability issue that may have application beyond a single measure is illustrated in the variability index. The index is a ratio of peak to off- peak variation in travel conditions. The interval differences (which represent 2 standard deviations above and below the average) in the peak periods are usually larger than in the off-peak and the variability index value is therefore greater than 1.0
- Travel Rate Index: this index does not use incident conditions for corridor /link studies so as to ensure that the limited sample of travel time data collected are not “skewed”. for an adequate but small n it provides an estimate of the recurring congestion along the corridor. TRI is computed mathematically the same way as the TTI (Travel Time Index).
- 80th percentile travel time is more sensitive to operations improvements and has been used in many studies for evaluating reliability. 80th percentile Travel Time Index = 80th percentile travel time / by free-flow travel time.(Lomax et al,2003)
- Percent Variation— this is a form of the statistical measure coefficient of variation and combines the average and standard deviation in a ratio. analysing travel time data sets using the coefficient of variation provides a clearer view of the trends and performance characteristics than the standard deviation by itself by removing trip length from the calculation. A factor of this type provides the ability to discuss the travel conditions of a variety of different trip lengths in a way similar to the travel rate index (SHRP 2, 2014)

2.1 Case study selection:

Four Arterials with parallel grade separators were selected for investigating effectiveness and efficiency. The analysis was done separately for each link and each direction in all cases and thus, the directional distance covered is 23.36 kms. These roadway sections over which travel time observations and statistics were calculated conformed to the following requisites to be comparable. The criteria used was firstly, they share the same spatial- temporal environment being in the same city, Nagpur. Hence the possibility of variability or ambiguity in interpretations due to these differences could be minimized and almost negligible. Secondly, data would be more consistent and results would be more comparable on all analytical parameters than other road links situated elsewhere, for analysis, validity and interpretation.

Figure 2: Parallel links of flyovers (Nagpur)

Thirdly, adjacency of both, the access control grade separator and the at-grade residual links qualify them as comparable links for ascertaining their respective differences as well as similarities on performance parameters (Figure 2 a and b)

Concepts used in the study: This study explores two concepts to determine how the two components of the link perform on the dimension of effectiveness and efficiency, Reliability and variability. Reliability: It is generally used in reference to the level of consistency in transportation service for a mode / trip/ route / corridor for a specific time. Conventionally reliability is use specific and has a user perspective i.e. it is derived from user perception based on their experience about a facility or system. Variability: It is the amount of inconsistency in operating conditions concerning transportation agencies and has a facility perspective. These measures are diagnostic and can inform the decision maker about issues like congestion and its frequency (Lomax et al.,2003)

For the study reliability statistics collected from real-time traffic data included only normal conditions and special or incidents influences were removed. Therefore only influence due to 1) Demand fluctuation, which is day-to-day variations caused by changes in activity levels or patterns 2) Traffic Control Devices such as signals or periodic signal events ;;citizenry. Direct and derived indicators using travel times and delay measures have been applied to elicit reliability, variability and vulnerability of the two links and thereby understand the degree of effectiveness and efficiency achieved by the access controlled links as compared to the residual multimodal link. The concepts are interlinked although their interpretations are distinct from each other.

3. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

The components which convey reliability of any link are the extent, intensity and variation of travel time from a user’s perception hence travel time reliability was obtained to find variability in performance of both links. The percent variation in travel time (run time) is found to be lesser in case of above grade. However, given the effective carriageway along the link lengths which are at grade the variation in travel time is stable at 18 % as shown (table 1) (figure-3)

Figure 3: Variation In Travel Time on Both Links (SE ranging between 0.04 - 3.29)

Derived and direct metrics: Direct metrics used were the standard descriptive statistics while six derived measures were used based on real time observations of travel time and the standard descriptive metrics. Delay time and carriageway capacity audit was also done.

Average travel time and travel time indices were calculated using observed data from the moving car method and videography. The skewness statistics for the peak period morning and evening indicate that the travel rate is a skewed data set having positive values and hence are right tailed distributions which are seen more particularly for signal stop time (delays) (Figure 4 and Figure 5a and b). A comparative matrix was constructed for analysis and interpretation of the various indices computed from the observations (Figure 6). All the indices for at grade segments of links show that travel time would be 2-3 times more during peak hours than free flow speeds. Thus, it is seen that the at grade links are less reliable during morning and evening peak hours as compared to above grade links where the travel time is between 1.5 to 1.8 times the travel time at FFS in mins/run between point A and B, which are the intersections connected by the grade separator.

The misery index for the at grade index is the highest computed value and by its nature shows maximum variation and hence unreliability of a link. An improvement in travel time was experienced under those conditions when signal synchronisation occurred which was observed from point A- B or B-A for 29 % of all readings for stop signals at grade. Similarly for ramp end exits it was 32 % of the trips at-grade and for the above grade links the ramp end exits with no signal occurred for 24% of trips.

Table 1: Effective Carriageway for Each Segment Along Links

FLYOVER	TOTAL ROAD WIDTH (In ms)	LINK SEGMENTS	LANE WIDTH BELOW FO (in ms)	PERCENT OF TOTAL AVAILAB LE	LANE WIDTH ABOVE FO (in ms)	PERCENT OF TOTAL AVAILAB LE
FO1	25	S1	10	40.00	10.62	42.48
	25	S2	9.5	38.00	10.62	
	25	S3	9.5	38.00	10.62	
	25	S4	8.5	34.00	10.62	
	25	S5	13.5	54.00	10.62	
	25	S6	13.5	54.00	10.62	
	25	S7	14	56.00	10.62	
	25	S8	9	36.00	10.62	
FO2	18	S1	12	66.67	10.69	59.37
	18	S2	9.5	52.78	10.69	
	18	S3	10	55.56	10.69	
	18	S4	8.5	47.22	10.69	
FO3	30	S1	11	36.67	10.89	36.30
	30	S2	7.5	25.00	10.89	
	30	S3	13	43.33	10.89	
	30	S4	7.5	25.00	10.89	
	30	S5	13	43.33	10.89	
	30	S6	9.5	31.67	10.89	
	30	S7	13	43.33	10.89	
	30	S8	10.5	35.00	10.89	
FO4	30	S1	13	43.33	11.92	39.73
	30	S2	11.5	38.33	11.92	
	30	S3	13	43.33	11.92	
	30	S4	10.5	35.00	11.92	

30	S5	12.5	41.67	11.92
30	S6	9.5	31.67	11.92
30	S7	13	43.33	11.92
30	S8	11.5	38.33	11.92

Table 2: Percentile Values Travel Time FO1

PERCENTILE	TOTAL JOURNEY TIME (in mins)	RUN TIME (in seconds)	TOTAL JOURNEY TIME (in mins)
10TH	2.95	2.76	2.13
25TH	3.15	2.96	2.20
50TH	3.69	3.18	2.34
75TH	4.30	3.44	2.49
80TH	4.45	3.52	2.53
90TH	4.64	4.04	2.72
95th	4.89	4.20	2.78
MEDIAN	3.36	3.18	2.34
MEAN	3.76	3.27	2.37

Table 2 shows the percentile values for travel time along FO1 situated in a residential cum institutional land use links studied. By computing the percentile values for travel times, the median value of travel time coincides with that of the 50th percentile and not the mean value which is higher. This is important as mostly the means are taken as measures more than medians and this could prove and give a non- realistic probability of an event occurring. Hence based on the skewness of the travel time distributions, the median is a better central tendency statistic to use as a base value for travel time for indices.

Figure 4: Skewness Ratio

Figure 5(a)

Figure 5(b)

The percentile distribution also shows the travel time variation more clearly. The variation is more pronounced at grade links than the above grade links. But given the motorised volume using the above grade and at grade links this could be attributed to many factors’ characteristic of at grade links on arterials in Indian cities. (Figure 7)

		F01	F02	F03	F04	F01	F02	F03	F04
		AT GRADE	AT GRADE	AT GRADE	AT GRADE	ABOVE GRADE	ABOVE GRADE	ABOVE GRADE	ABOVE GRADE
1	MISERY INDEX (UNIT NONE)	2.71	2.93	3.15	1.95	1.97	2.22	1.55	1.81
2	TRAVEL TIME INDEX / TRAVEL	2.01	2.28	1.78	1.23	1.67	1.83	1.31	1.38
3	80TH PERCENTILE TRAVEL TIME INDEX	1.89	2.63	2.00	1.39	1.78	2.00	1.44	1.58
4	VARIABILITY INDEX	2.65	1.09	1.11	1.11	1.00	1.50	1.25	1.00

Figure 6: Comparative Index Matrix

Figure 7: Mode Split of Motorized Traffic

Instead of the TTI the travel rate index used in the study was to ascertain incident free mobility between endpoints of the links. The length differences between all links studied offers an interesting outcome, the longer the length of a link the more the variation in travel times especially at grade. But for shorter segments the travel time variation is marginal for both at grade and above grade. If this outcome is analysed qualitatively the road side friction is lesser for shorter commutes as compared to longer commutes and hence for shorter segments the presence of a grade separator hardly makes any difference to travel time gain by users. This factor is again ratified by the travel rate index and the variability index values for all the FO's. The percent variation graph shows a similar trend. The link audits showed that the effective carriageway width available above grade was 10.00 meters and at grade the carriageway width reduced by a range of 3-5 meters on either side of the grade separator /flyover. Thus, reducing the effective carriageway width by almost 40 % which would have been available at either ends otherwise. This is another cause of speed reductions and travel time variation. Caution and possibility of bottlenecks cause drivers to slow down in at least two segments of at grade links either way. Speed reductions characterize all mobility occurring on at grade links. (figure 8). If such design geometrics are present in heterogenous traffic streams then the effect on travel times is most certainly going to be exponential in case of incidences and events. The average volume split also indicate that the above grade links are used by traffic volume ranging between 35 to 48 % of the total volume on the corridor at peak times out of which the at-grade volume non-motorised comprise 18-22% traffic and the above grade comprise almost 60 % of overall traffic (Figure 9, Figure 10 a and b)

Figure 8: Speed Reductions at Grade Sections

4. DISCUSSION

This empirical study compares the efficiency and efficacy of the grade separator as an access control link with that of its residual component the at grade link. The paper investigates the average conditions in which travel time reliability is obtained as also how often and how much does the performance varies from the average. The study was not framed to analyse observations during incidents, inclement weather conditions or events since it was the aim to explore the efficacy and effectiveness of the set of links individually and as a pair. Which it has achieved using a variety of indices as tools along with link audits for road characteristics. Reliability and variability are the two concepts on which the study was anchored/ based.

Reliability thus

above grade links when compared to at-grade links. And demand is a determinant of the amount of traffic volume traversing a link or its attraction appeal for a link. Therefore, when demand is higher than carriageway capacity, travel times are bound to be higher on links which is what happened in the case of all at grade links which have access to goods and services which are more desirable than the straight trajectories and negligible access points between point a and b.

PERCENT TRAFFIC SPLIT ON LINKS

Figure 9

MODAL SPLIT AT GRADE

Figure 10 a

Modal split above grade

Figure 10 b

During nighttime all things being equal the two links would register similar if not same travel times. Although travel time reliability is important as part of the planning, traffic management, and system maintenance processes it has been frugally used as a performance metric which has been attempted in the paper.

The empirical study / investigation proves that the variability in travel times and signal delays of the at grade links are found

to be greater when compared to the above grade links and is obviously the prime reason for their use by the private vehicles which are necessarily faster modes and less passenger intensive. But for freight, other delivery vehicles, heavy motor vehicles or the non-motorized transport the benefit of travel time savings is not transferred instead they are compounded due to the fact they compulsorily traverse the at grade links which have constrained capacity and side friction which slows traffic streams in both directions. In heterogenous conditions, where such interventions are provided, while aiding motorized modes to move at higher speeds relegate other modes like HMV's, pedestrians and other NMT's to other low-capacity links.

5. CONCLUSION

This study commenced with the observation that the fast moving modes are mostly the selected modes of transport when a grade separation intervention is suggested implying that the benefit of travel time is determinedly skewed consciously propelling citizens to use and turn to more fuel intense and non-sustainable modes rather than giving impetus to public transit systems or NMTs which are not only sustainable but also more feasible and even today the most preferred mode in the Indian context. Inequity is observed when conditions favour specific modes on one link while relegating other predominant modes which maybe slower to other road links. This also creates a domino effect as this in turn reduces their capacity, increase vehicular friction and road density and in the process transfers congestion from one location to another not completely removing it from the system. There are two implications of these results for future research and existing practice.

Further research can be to understand how travel times vary over extended links comprising of variety of / combination of road typology and different seasons or in a year. This would give inputs which could be incorporated in decision making and planning strategies for a segment, area or even at city level. Links at grade become prone and susceptible to disruptions or unnecessary delays to users when there is non-uniform carriageway available to travel as space restrictions are imposed due to ramp structures built on or along the medians as is the case with most Flyovers in Indian cities. Planners need to rethink about such retrofits to existing arterials before their provision becomes a decision hard to rescind after they become functional. With vehicular volumes increasing, and constraining capacities of links, the study is significant and relevant as a catalyst to trigger in depth study whenever new development projects are being sanctioned without duly considering the outcome of such decisions. With the physical and traffic attributes of the urban arterials in Indian cities it is a challenge to accommodate capacity enhancing interventions and for them to be truly effective and reliable as mobility enhancers.

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